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Internal Audit Functions And Financial Reporting Quality Of Public Sector In Rivers State.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of internal audit functions on financial reporting quality of public sector in Rivers State, with specific objective such as: examine the effect of procedural audit on faithful representation in public sector organizations in Rivers State; ascertain the effect of financial audit on faithful representation in public sector organizations in Rivers State. The study employed survey research design. The population twenty-six (26) ministries, departments and agencies (MDA's) of Rivers State government, judgmental sampling technique was adopted in this study and 11 MDA were judgmentally selected due to proximity with two hundred (200) respondents from Budgets department, Finance department and Accounts department, Procurements department, Monitoring department and Office of the Commissioner for each ministry selected. The result of the study revealed that: there is no significant effect of procedural audit on faithful representation in public sector organizations in Rivers State; there is a significant effect of financial audit on faithful representation in public sector organizations in Rivers State. The study concluded that internal audit function has a significant effect on financial reporting quality of public sector in Rivers State. The study recommended that the management of MDAs in Rivers State should create independent audit units to carry out their audit functions independently in order to have effective internal control system that will lead to sound audit report;; the quality of audit should be maintained and improved upon by keeping audit objectives such as financial control mechanisms, implementation of Acts, rules and regulations

INTRODUCTION

A lack of transparency and accountability in the public sector presents a risk to the efficiency of financial stability, long term economic sustainability, economic growth and development. Internal audit and control systems are vital in ensuring financial reporting quality for the use of public funds, safeguarding public resources against corruption and other misappropriation and unlawful practices. Risk is inherent in the decisions that an organization manage and assist in the achievement of business objectives. That is why establishing, implementing and embedding effective risk and control elements of the overall corporate governance framework are fundamental to all organizations. Internal audit is an assurance role in an organization's governance processes, particularly in risk management and control. In many organizations, the expectations upon internal audit have increased. In sum, according to prior literature, a high-quality internal audit functions can contribute to financial reporting quality because it is more likely to detect and deter opportunistic or biased judgments made by management (Prawitt et al. 2025).

A commonly used definition for internal audit is: 'An independent, objective assurance and consulting activity designed to add value and improve an organization's operations. It helps an organization accomplish its objectives by bringing a systematic, disciplined approach to evaluate and improve the effectiveness of risk management, control and governance processes in the workplace. This definition recognizes two roles for internal audit: to provide an independent assurance service to the board, audit committee and management, focusing on reviewing the effectiveness of the governance, risk management

and control processes that management has put into place to provide advice to management on governance risks and controls, for example, the controls that will be needed when undertaking new business ventures.

Building on the definition above, the Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA) has issued professional standards for both assurance and consulting works. Public sector organizations in Nigeria are likely to follow internal auditing standards and guidance set by the Constitution and other public sectors related bodies such as the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN) and the Association of National Accountants of Nigeria (ANAN). Internal audit is vital to the function of an organization because it is considered a valuable tool for increasing the financial information quality and ensuring the validity of financial reporting. An internal audit is a management tool used in ensuring transparency in the conduct of business in both the private and public sectors. It is vital to have an effective and efficient internal audit in an organization (Kinsella, 2020) because it serves as an effective means for monitoring and promoting a system of good governance in any organization (Belay, 2020; Kangarlouei et al., 2020). The responsibilities for the internal audit function rest with the internal auditors, who in turn rely a great deal on the soundness and effectiveness of the internal control system.

Statement of the Problem

Many business organizations are rapidly assuming complexity resulting in reliance on internal audit for a way of control. Despite the existence of internal audit departments in these organizations, it is argued that the rate of fraud and misdeeds is still on the increase, particularly in the public sector. Some people argued that internal auditors are creating more problems while others see them as tools for witch-hunting and therefore see them as an unnecessary evil. The internal control system in Nigeria public sector may be insufficient based on some identified factors like; lack of proper assignment of duties as well as a shortage of qualified staff to carry out internal audit and accounting duties; lack of implementation of the routine audit report by appropriate authorities; inadequacy of internal control system leading to an improper investigation.

Perhaps, the internal audit has not achieved the desired objective in public organizations in Nigeria, as demonstrated by the kind of frauds and deception in the public sector (Njui, 2024). Some examples of the bizarre frauds being in 2018, “a mystery snake is said to have sneaked into the accounts office of the Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board, JAMB, in Makurdi, the Benue State capital and made away with N36 million cash”. In 2025, the gorilla was said to have swallowed 6.8 million Naira (the equivalent of more than \$19,000). The money in question is said to be entrance fees collected by the zoo’s patrons, especially during the Eid-ul-Fitri holidays.

International Federation of Accountants (IFAC) determined to stem the tide of high-profile corporate failures across the globe over the last ten (10) years. They developed new legislation, standards, codes and guidelines. This study, therefore, examined the relationship between internal audit function and financial reporting quality of public sector organizations in Nigeria, with particular emphasis on Rivers State. It also shows the dimensions of internal audit functions as Procedural audit, and Financial Audit, and the measures of financial reporting quality, faithful representation.

Aims and Objectives of the Study

This study investigated the relationship between internal audit functions and financial reporting quality of public sector in Rivers State. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. Examine the effect of procedural audit on faithful representation in public sector organizations in Rivers State.
- ii. Determine the effect of financial audit on faithful representation in public sector organizations in Rivers State.

Research Questions

Based on the specific objective, the following research questions are raised to include the following:

- i. What is the effect of procedural audit on faithful representation in public sector organizations in Rivers State?
- ii. What is the effect of financial audit on faithful representation public sector organizations in Rivers State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were found relevant to the above stated problems and objectives and thus presented in the null form here.

HO₁: There is no significant effect of procedural audit on faithful representation in public sector organizations in Rivers State.

HO₂: There is no significant effect of financial audit on faithful representation in public sector organizations in Rivers State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Internal Audit Functions

A commonly used definition for internal audit is “An independent, objective assurance and consulting activity designed to add value and improve an organization’s operations”. A variety of meanings have been attributed to the term ‘internal auditing’. The concept of internal auditing is a popular concept in auditing and accounting literature and as such many authors and professional bodies have provided definitions of the concept. In its simplest term, internal audit is an audit conducted in respect of the affairs of an organization by its employees or by an external service provider (Eke, 2022). This definition recognizes that internal auditing is performed by the employees of an organization and focuses on the operations of the enterprise; it also indicates that the internal audit function can be outsourced to a vendor who perform same tasks as in-house internal auditors and report to management.

Internal auditing as an audit that is carried out by the specialist staff of the organization being audited and concern itself mainly with the routine checking of accounting transactions daily, with the object of quickly locating irregularities, thus making it more difficult for fraud to be perpetrated, because of the constant nature of the checking. This definition, which is one of the traditional definitions of internal auditing is quite comprehensive and brings out clearly the various features and objects of internal auditing. It emphasizes the fact that internal auditing focuses on accounting transactions and as such narrowly reflects the basic role of internal auditors. The Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA), Millichamp (2021), Eke (2022), initially defined internal auditing as an independent appraisal activity within an organization for the review of accounting, financial and other operations as a basis for service to management; it is a managerial control, which functions by measuring and evaluating the effectiveness of other controls. This definition indicates that internal auditing is not mainly concerned with routine checking of accounting records but goes beyond the accounting records and includes reviewing and reporting on the operational performance of an organization.

From the perspective of Aguolu (2022), internal auditing is the independent appraisal of the functions and quality of performance of an organization by a specially assigned staff as part of the internal control system. He pointed out that many organizations, especially very large ones, engage the services of internal auditors to enhance the efficiency of their operations; and that the internal auditor is an employee of the organization and hence works full time within the organization. This definition is like the one originally given by the IIA because of its focus on the independence of the internal auditor. All the definitions given above tend to emphasize the fact that internal auditing involves reviewing the accounting and financial operations of an organization and is undertaken by the employees of the organization. However, modern internal auditing now extends beyond reviewing transactions to evaluating operational and strategic risks and is undertaken as an assurance and consulting activity that improves the operations of an entity. It is based on the strategic role of internal auditing that the Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA) via its Professional Practices Framework (PPF) issued in 2022, modified its original definition of internal auditing.

The new definition of internal auditing is designed to accommodate the profession’s expanding role and responsibilities. Thus, the IIA (2022) defined internal auditing as an independent, objective assurance and consulting activity designed to add value and improve an organization’s operations. It helps an organization accomplish its objectives by bringing a systematic discipline ed approach to evaluate and improve the effectiveness of risk management, control, and governance processes. Internal auditors carry out various tasks in the performance of their functions. Since internal auditors work on behalf of and

report to management, the tasks they perform are dictated by management. Thus, the peculiar nature of an organization and demand of management determines the scope and nature of internal audit work.

Procedural Audit

Procedural audit involves the evaluation of internal controls, accounting policies, and other procedures of a project execution and management by the ministries by the internal auditor. Procedural Audit is a means of testing whether controls are in place and are being followed. It involves evaluating the effectiveness of the design and implementation of internal controls, to detect and prevent material misstatement (Aren, 2024). Procedural audit requires regular reviews and reports by which management or those authorizing it would work with. According to business parrot (2023), with procedural audit, an overall appraisal may be made of the entire business, or the audit may be directed to a particular business segment. At the conclusion of the audit, management receives a report that will list the findings. Furthermore, these audits are normally performed by the internal audit staff in many companies and take place during the entire year. The report concluded that where a company does not have an internal audit staff, it may hire the auditor that certifies its financial statements to perform a procedural review as part of the annual audit. When such an arrangement is made, management expects to receive a separate report on this review, offering its findings with recommendations (business Parrot, 2023).

It is argued that one of the ways by which procedural audit could be effectively executed by the internal audit is the use of approval and authorization system of internal audit (ICSC, 2025). Approval and authorization system of internal control is described as one of the internal audit systems that ensure that assets are safeguarded, resources are managed so as to get better results by the organization. Approval and authorization systems simply entail that authorizing and executing transactions and events are only done by persons acting within the scope of their authority. Authorization is the principal means of ensuring that only valid transactions and events initiated as intended by management. Furthermore, authorization procedures must be documented and clearly communicated to managers and employees; it should include the specific conditions and terms under which authorizations are to be made in addition, conforming to the terms of an authorization means that employees act in accordance with directives and within the limitations established by management or legislation (ICSC, 2024). It is believed that where there are authorization and approval systems in place and religiously followed, controls can be established and resources management enhanced.

As it relates to purchases, the standard operating procedures for the procedural audit department in the post audit verification process includes the following: Checking that the invoices are correctly coded according to the ledger accounts classification; Verifying that appropriate acknowledgements (such as initials and signatures) appears accurately on each of the purchase documents presented; Verifying that each correct invoice has been passed for payment; Checking that each invoice is entered into the invoice register; Checking that each invoice has been posted to the purchase ledger account; Investigating into the nature of outstanding orders; Enquiring into unprocessed invoices; Checking additions contained in the invoice register; Confirming if the purchase invoice register is in agreement with the purchase accounts total.

In relation to sales, the audit objective is to ensure that sales proceeds are deposited into the bank account, that all documentations such as invoices are accurately prepared, properly authorized and recorded in the books of accounts to avoid understatement or overstatement of sales and delivery made to customer (business parrot, 2023). With effective internal controls established via the internal audit function, several aspects of the organization are impacted. Risk is minimized as well as optimum resources use can be achieved. Approval and authorization systems ensure that this is achieved. Furthermore, risk management has to do with identification, analysis and control of such risks that threaten resources, assets, personnel and the earning capacity of a company (Mwazo et al.,2023). According to Dorfman (2007), risk management is the logical development and implementation of a plan to deal with potential losses. It is important for an organization to put in place risk management programs so as to manage its exposure to risks as well as protect its assets. The essence is to prepare ahead of time on how to control and finance losses before they occur. Dorfman continues to say that risk management is a strategy of pre-loss planning for pre-loss resources and approval and authorization system is a means of risk control. To

manage government resources efficiently, there must be internal controls that are sound to assist in collection of tax claims as per the regulations in the literature from different research entities, where internal control models were developed (Briciu et al, 2021).

Financial Audit

Financial Audit is an independent, objective evaluation of the ministries' financial reports and financial reporting processes so that resources management and transparency of activities could be attained (Aren, 2024). Aren further explained that a financial audit is conducted to provide an opinion whether financial statements (the information being verified) are stated in accordance with specified criteria. Normally, the criteria are international accounting standards, although auditors may conduct audits of financial statements prepared using the cash basis or some other basis of accounting (accruals basis for public organizations) appropriate for the organization. In providing an opinion whether financial statements are fairly stated in accordance with accounting standards, the auditor gathers evidence to determine whether the statements contain material errors or other misstatements. In discussing the sufficiency and appropriateness of audit evidence, Chukwu et al. (2019) noted that the sources of the evidence and procedures adopted in obtaining those sources must be reliable for an effective evaluation of management assertions.

Furthermore, in accordance with the international accounting standards such US GAAP, auditors must release an opinion of the overall financial statements in the auditor's report. Auditors can release three types of statements other than an unqualified/unmodified opinion. The unqualified auditor's opinion is the opinion that the financial statements are presented fairly. A qualified opinion is that the financial statements are presented fairly in all material respects in accordance with US GAAP, except for a material misstatement that does not however pervasively affect the user's ability to rely on the financial statements. A qualified opinion can also be issued for a scope limitation that is of limited significance. Further the auditor can instead issue a disclaimer, because there is insufficient and appropriate evidence to form an opinion or because of lack of independence. In a disclaimer the auditor explains the reasons for withholding an opinion and explicitly indicates that no opinion is expressed. Finally, an adverse audit opinion is issued when the financial statements do not present fairly due to departure from US GAAP and the departure materially affects the financial statements overall. In an adverse auditor's report, the auditor must explain the nature and size of the misstatement and must state the opinion that the financial statements do not present fairly in accordance with US GAAP (The Institute of Chartered Accountants of India, 2022)

Financial audits where they are to be done by external auditors are typically performed by firms of practicing accountants who are experts in financial reporting. The financial audit is one of many assurance functions provided by accounting firms (Arens, 2024). Many organizations separately employ or hire internal auditors, who do not attest to financial reports but focus mainly on the internal controls of the organization. External auditors may choose to place limited reliance on the work of internal auditors. To achieve the purpose of external audit, the external auditor implements a planned audit process that is well documented (Ordu et al., 2019). Auditing promotes transparency and accuracy in the financial disclosures made by an organization, therefore would likely reduce such organization's concealment of unscrupulous dealings (Christodoulou, 2021).

Worthy of note is that the International Standards on Auditing (ISA) issued by the International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (IAASB) is considered as the benchmark for audit process. Almost all jurisdictions require auditors to follow the ISA or a local variation of the ISA. As such, private and public institution regardless of the country are required to follow the guideline towards conduction auditing – whether internal or external. Financial audits exist to add credibility to the implied assertion by an organization's management that its financial statements fairly represent the organization's position and performance to the firm's stakeholders. The principal stakeholders of a company are typically its shareholders (for private entities) while the public (for public entities), but other parties such as tax authorities, banks, regulators, suppliers, customers and employees may also have an interest in knowing that the financial statements are presented fairly, in all material aspects. An audit is not designed to provide absolute assurance, being based on sampling and not the testing of all transactions and balances;

rather it is designed to reduce the risk of a material financial statement misstatement whether caused by fraud or error (Christodoulou, 2021). A misstatement is defined in ISA 450 as an error, omitted disclosure or inappropriate accounting policy. "Material" is an error or omission that would affect the users' decision (The Institute of Chartered Accountants of India, 2022).

Audits exist because they add value through easing the cost of information asymmetry and reducing information risk, not because they are required by law (audits are obligatory in many EU-member States and in many jurisdictions are obligatory for companies listed on public stock exchanges). The Institute of Chartered Accountants of India, (2022) explains that for collection and accumulation of audit evidence, certain methods and means generally adopted by auditors include: 1) Posting checking; 2) Testing the existence and effectiveness of management controls that prevent financial statement misstatement; 3) Casting checking; 4) Physical examination and count; 5) Confirmation; 6) Inquiry; 7) Observation; 8) inspection; 9) Year-end scrutiny; 10) Re-computation; 11) Tracing in subsequent period; 12) Bank reconciliation; 13) Vouching; 14) Verification of existence, ownership, title and value of assets and determination of the extent and nature of liabilities

Financial Reporting Quality

Amadi et al. (2024) observed that financial reporting quality is a complex construct for which there is no generally accepted definition. Because of its complexity, there are a number of quantitative measures used in measuring financial reporting quality. These measures include audit report lag (Chukwu et al., 2024) and value relevance of financial information (Chukwu et al., 2025). There are also a number of qualitative measures based on the qualitative characteristics of useful financial statements. In this work, financial reporting quality was measured using faithful representation, a fundamental qualitative characteristic in the IASB conceptual framework. Prior study has addressed the relationship between internal auditing functions and financial reporting in many ways. Financial reports are product that are jointly owned by management and an independent auditor (Hogan & Wilkins 2008). On the other hand, most prior research focused on the relationship between internal control quality and financial reporting quality.

Prawitt et. al. (2025) stated that IAF of US companies by using six individual components as a dimension based on external auditing standards (AICPA SAS No. 65 (2020) provide evidence that IAF quality is associated with better financial reporting quality. Davidson et. al. (2024) reveals that IAF established voluntarily is not significantly related to higher financial reporting quality in an Australian setting. However, the study does not consider firms' individual IAF quality. Brown et al. (2021) find an increase in financial reporting quality after the implementation of KonTraG, a law requiring an enhanced internal control system. However, this event study does not consider firms' individual IAF quality and thereby seems to assume a rather constant level of IAF quality among firms.

Faithful Representation

The quality of financial reports is for it to be faithfully represented to make them qualitative and make decision useful. This agrees with the objective of financial reporting that explains the need to provide financial information related to reporting entity that is useful to investors, lenders and other creditors in making decisions about providing resources to the entity (Enyi et al., 2024). Those organizations that are publicly listed have a duty to report adequately to stakeholders. This makes the activities of firms to be transparent, as well as make management to be accountable (IASB, 2020).

The main objectives of reporting finances centered on the provision of financial information that is useful to financial analyst, investors, creditors, lenders, government and other stakeholders; for making a sound financial decision, for the assessment of certainty of future cash flows and also for reporting the economic resources and obligations of a business (Dyckman et al., 2001).

The soul of accounting is a true financial reporting quality. The more the quality of financial reports the more the truth are revealed, the more they are qualitative. High-quality accounting information is the lifeblood of capital markets (IASB, 2020). Financial information should be more than any information that is relevant, true, complete and free of error. Financial reports are also expected to be comparable, understandable, timely and verifiable. Financial reports present accounting information to various users (stakeholders); reflecting assets, equity, liabilities, expenses and income among other financial information.

These reports are in the form of statements vital for making economic decisions as well as required for appraising performance over defined time frame. Documenting financial transactions, which later leads to financial statements; has been acknowledged as one of the most frequent business practices across departments (Laskin, 2023). Therefore, the need for quality financial reporting is significant to today accounting.

However, financial reporting history across the globe has revealed cases of accounting scandals. Bakre (2007) states that investors in Nigeria and all around the world lost billions of naira through the connivance of external auditors, accountants and managers of companies to manipulate financial statements. These scandals occurred in the face of accounting standards, accounting regulations, internal and external auditing. It is presumed that there should be no financial misreporting when these factors are in place, but they occurred. Kothari et. al. (2023) expressed the role of management in providing financial information to investors, but the volume of literature on earnings management shows that managers misrepresent companies' financial performance to suit themselves.

Agency Theory

Jensen & Meckling (1976) developed the agency theory and in explaining the theory viewed the firm as a nexus of contracts between different stakeholders of the organization. They pointed out that the owners and executives of an organization may have differences in opinion regarding the best interests of the organization. The objective of agency theory is to determine optimal contract between the principal and the agent. The agent tries to maximize personal gains by satisfying principal's economic objectives and as such the agent's commitment level is a function of perceived reward value for satisfying principal's objectives. The agency theory is based on the agency relationship. Jensen & Meckling (1976) pointed out that an agency relationship is one in which one or more persons (the principal) engage another person (the agent) to perform some service on their behalf which involves delegating some decision-making authority to the agent. Perhaps, the most recognizable form of agency relationship is that of an employer and employee. Other examples include state (principal) and ambassador (agent); constituents (principal) and elected representative (agent); organization (principal) and lobbyist (agent); or shareholders (principal) and board of directors (agent).

Thus, the relationship between the principal and the agent based on the contract is a focal point of agency theory. Principal wants to maximize his/her benefits while minimizing reward to the agent at the same time. On the other hand, the agent wants to maximize his/her benefits. Two problems addressed by the theory are: The first problems arise because the desires and goals of the principal may not match with those of agent thus a conflict, and the fact that the principal is unable to validate the agent's activities; second is the problems that arise because the principal and agent may be having different appetite concerning risk and each be inclined to take diverse arrangements. The basic assumption of agency theory is that the principal's wealth, per se, would not be maximized because of the following reasons: (1) The agent and the principal have different goals; (2) The agent and the principal have different access to information; thus, the principal cannot effectively monitor what the agent does and know which information the agent has; and (3) The agent and principal have different propensity towards risk.

Agency Theory by Adams (1994) explains it is used to explain the relationship between activities of external and internal auditors. Furthermore, the theory is useful for highlighting the internal auditor functions in both private and public organization and therefore anchor this study on agency theory.

Empirical Review

Al-Qadasi, et al (2025). Carried out an investigation to seek to answer concerns about the sufficiency of traditional corporate reporting by examining the influence of the internal audit function's (IAF) qualities on integrated reporting quality (IRQ) and the moderating effect of corporate social responsibility committee's (CSRC). Even though integrated reporting (IR) is becoming more significant, nothing is known about the function of IAF in this setting. This study uses ordinary least squares regressions, integrating two-way cluster-robust standard errors (clustered by firm and year), to examine the association between the quality IAF and IRQ, as well as the moderating influence of CSRC, for companies listed in Malaysia spanning the period from 2017 to 2020. Analyzing data from Malaysian-listed firms (2017–2020), findings show that increased IAF investments are associated with lower IRQ, particularly in the

presence of a CSRC. However, firms with in-house show a positive association with higher IRQ, which is amplified by a CSRC. This suggests a complementary relationship between CSRC and in-house IAF, potentially guiding regulatory practices regarding CSR or sustainability committees. Thus, the presence of CSRC signifies the organization's dedication to the advancement of sustainable development principles. This study's implications include promoting stronger internal mechanisms such as IAFs and CSRCs, which will ultimately improve IRQ. This research contributes to understanding the combined impact of IAF and CSRC on reporting quality by focusing on them as key governance components influencing both financial and non-financial reporting. As a result, regulators and practitioners can gain insights to improve IR efficacy and stakeholder decision-making.

Fatikasari and Kuntadi, (2025). Conducted a Literature Review article on The Effect of Audit Experience, Competence, and Objectivity on the Effectiveness of the Internal Audit Function is a scientific article that builds research hypotheses between variables used in further research. The method of writing this Literature Review article is the library research method, which is sourced from online media such as Goggle Scholar and other academic online media. The results of this literature review article are: 1) Audit Experience affects the Effectiveness of the Internal Audit Function; 2) Competence affects the Effectiveness of the Internal Audit Function; and 3) Objectivity affects the Effectiveness of the Internal Audit Function.

Mandal, (2025). examine how auditors perceive the influence of crucial fraud prevention factors in deterring financial statement fraud within the corporate sector. Additionally, this research explores the mediating effect of fraud awareness in elucidating the impact of ethical leadership and internal control systems on preventing financial statement fraud. The study used an online survey, targeting a sample of 141 professionally qualified auditors with at least one year of practical experience in the field. The researchers used "Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)" to examine relationships between latent variables using partial least squares structural equation modeling. The study investigated the impact of whistleblowing systems, fraud awareness, ethical leadership, internal control systems and corporate governance on fraud prevention. This research finding provides evidence to the corporate sector by establishing the significance of fraud awareness as the most influencing factor in preventing financial statement fraud. Furthermore, the combined explanatory variables account for 77.4% of the overall variance in financial statement fraud prevention. The study reveals a partial mediation effect of fraud awareness on the relationship between the internal control system and financial statement fraud prevention.

Hazaea, et al (2025). Examines the existing literature on internal audit (IA) in the United States to identify how internal audit functions (IAFs) have evolved in response to global shifts in business practices. Despite growing attention to IA, the literature remains fragmented, limiting a comprehensive understanding of how IA has evolved in response to business practices. Through a systematic review, this study analyzes 171 studies published between 1984 and 2023 retrieved from the Scopus database. This study investigates the characteristics of the literature and topics discussed, focusing on six key aspects: the practice of IA, the role of IA, the quality of IA, information technology (IT) auditing, risk management, and the relationship between IA and other parties. The results reveal a paradigm shift in the activities undertaken by internal auditors and a significant transition in the literature from discussing traditional topics to new topics related to environmental changes, the climate crisis, geopolitical challenges, and technological developments. The results also emphasize the need for more theory-based, empirical, and comparative studies on IA in different contexts and sectors. This paper identifies substantial gaps in IA literature and proposes directions for future research agendas, particularly concerning the influence of politics, culture, and the effects of COVID-19 on IA practices. These insights provide valuable guidance for IA practitioners, researchers, standard setters, and the Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA) in refining frameworks and understanding global IA trends.

Nurhaliza and Kuntadi (2025). Examines the factors influencing the effectiveness of internal audit functions, with a focus on Auditor Experience, Management Support, and Internal Control Effectiveness. Experienced auditors possess a deeper understanding of internal processes and risk controls, which are critical to maintaining audit integrity. Management support ensures that internal auditors have access to

the necessary resources and autonomy to execute their duties effectively, thereby enhancing the audit's credibility among stakeholders such as top management and boards of directors. Internal control effectiveness refers to a system's capacity to prevent or detect non-compliance and fraud, necessitating comprehensive knowledge of operational procedures, business risks, and advanced analytical skills to evaluate control systems. This study aims to provide a nuanced understanding and establish robust hypotheses on the interrelationships between these factors in internal audits, ultimately improving audit effectiveness across various sectors. The literature review reveals that: (1) auditor experience significantly influences internal audit effectiveness, (2) management support is pivotal to effective auditing, and (3) robust internal controls are essential for ensuring the integrity of audit functions.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted survey research design. The targeted population of this study consists of twenty-six (26) ministries, departments and agencies (MDA's) of Rivers State government. The research adopted judgmental (purposive) sampling and 11 MDA were judgmentally selected due to proximity, 5 departments were selected from each MDA, which are (Budgets department, Finance and Accounts department, Procurements department, Monitoring department and Office of the Commissioner), which brings the total department to 55 with 4 questionnaire each department amounting to two hundred twenty (220) respondents.

EMPIRICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Questionnaire Distribution

Numbers	Questionnaire	Percentage (%)
No. Sent out	220	100%
No. Returned	170	77%
No. Not Returned	50	23%

Table 4.1 shows the distribution and collection of questionnaires sent to the respondents. It was shown that 220 copies of questionnaires were distributed to the respondents representing 100%. 170 copies of questionnaires representing 77% were correctly filled and successfully collected from the respondents; however, 50 copies of the questionnaires representing 23% were not collected. However, the researcher used the 170 copies of questionnaires correctly filled to represent 100% as the basis for the analysis.

Descriptive Statistics on all Variables of the Study

		Financial Audit	Procedural Audit	Faithful Representation
N	Valid	170	170	170
	Missing	0	0	0
Mean		3.10	3.07	3.00
Std. Deviation		1.267	1.313	1.287

Table 4.5 shows the descriptive Statistics of all variables of the study. It was shown that financial audit had a mean value of 3.10 and a standard deviation of 1.267; procedural audit had a mean value of 3.07 and a standard deviation of 1.313; faithful representation had a mean value of 3.00 and a standard deviation of 1.287; The mean of all the variables of the study were above 3.0. Therefore, the researcher upheld the prevalence of the variable.

Descriptive Statistics on Items of Financial Audit

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Regular and timely preparation of Financial statements by the ministry could lead to efficient resources management	170	527	3.10	1.267
Compliance to financial standards and regulations toward financial reports and transactions could lead to efficient resources management	170	588	3.28	1.198
Transparency of financial transaction and activities through proper documentations and visibility of such documents to the internal auditor could lead to efficient resources management	170	541	3.18	1.362
Valid N (list wise)	170			

The table shows the descriptive statistics on items of financial audit. It was shown that Regular and timely preparation of financial statements by the ministry could lead to efficient resources management had a mean value of 3.10 and a standard deviation of 1.267; Compliance to financial standards and regulations toward financial reports and transactions could lead to efficient resources management had a mean value of 3.28 and a standard deviation of 1.198; Transparency of financial transaction and activities through proper documentations and visibility of such documents to the internal auditor could lead to efficient resources management had a mean value of 3.18 and a standard deviation of 1.362. The mean of all the variables of the study were above 3.0. Therefore, the researcher upheld the prevalence of the variable.

Descriptive Statistics on Items of Procedural Audit

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Measuring and evaluating the effectiveness of internal control could bring about financial reporting quality in the ministry.	170	522	3.07	1.313
Adhering to relevant accounting system and policies could lead to effective resources management within the system (Ministry)	170	536	3.15	1.278
Adhering to policies and procurement provision towards projects execution could lead to efficient resources management	170	553	3.25	1.197
Valid N (list wise)	170			

The table shows the descriptive statistics on items of procedural audit. It was shown that Measuring and evaluating the effectiveness of internal control could bring about financial reporting quality in the ministry had a mean value of 3.07 and a standard deviation of 1.313; Adhering to relevant accounting system and policies could lead to effective resources management within the system (Ministry had a mean value of 3.15 and a standard deviation of 1.278; while Adhering to policies and procurement provision towards projects execution could lead to efficient resources management had a mean value of 3.25 and a standard deviation of 1.197. The mean of all the variables of the study were above 3.0. Therefore, the researcher upheld the prevalence of the variable.

Descriptive Statistics on Items of Faithful Representation

Descriptive Statistics				
	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Internal audit function will help ministry to be up to date on all compliance regulations.	170	506	3.00	1.287
Internal audit functions will help accounting setting standard that could help to enable funds are apply for productive means	170	505	3.02	1.275
Internal audit function will help to ensure all faithful representation of financial reports are adhere to	170	524	3.08	1.330
Valid N (listwise)	170			

The table shows the descriptive statistics on items of faithful representation. It was shown that Internal audit function will help ministry to be up to date on all compliance regulations had a mean value of 3.00 and a standard deviation of 1.287; Internal audit functions will help accounting setting standard that could help to enable funds are apply for productive means had a mean value of 3.02 and a standard deviation of 1.275; while Internal audit function will help to ensure all faithful representation of financial reports are adhere to had a mean value of 3.08 and a standard deviation of 1.330. The mean of all the variables of the study were above 3.0. Therefore, the researcher upheld the prevalence of the variable.

Results of Correlation Analysis

		PCA	FA	FR
PCA	Pearson Correlation	1	-.157*	.248**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.015	.000
	N	170	170	170
FA	Pearson Correlation	-.157*	1	-.318**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.015		.000
	N	170	170	170
FR	Pearson Correlation	.248**	-.318**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	170	170	170

Source: Researcher’s SPSS (v.27) computation Result, 2025

The results of the correlation analysis as shown in the table above, indicated that the relationship between procedural audit and financial audit was negative but statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance ($r = -0.157$; $p < 0.05$). Also, the correlation between faithful representation and financial audit is negative but significant ($r = -0.318$; $p < 0.05$)

Regression for Model One (FR Model)

Model one considers the effect of internal audit function (i.e. procedural audit and financial audit on faithful representation (FR). The results of data analysis with the help of computer processing based on SPSS version 27.0 calculations obtained multiple regression equations based on the following output.

Coefficients Result on FR Model

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	17.183	.838		20.493	.000		
	PCA	-.033	.085	.043	-0.388	.599	.591	1.693
	FA	-.239	.062	-.311	-3.860	.000	.591	1.693

a. Dependent Variable: FR

Model Summary

Model	R	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	Durbin-Watson
1	.897 ^a	.805	2.64641	.805	10.647	2	169	.000	1.829

a. Predictors: (Constant), PCA, FA

b. Dependent Variable: FR

The table of the above regression result, R-square value is recorded as 0.805, which suggested 80.5% of the changes in the faithful representation (FR) is accounted for by the independent variables (PCA, and FA), while 19.5% of the variation remained unexplained. This remaining percentage could be caused by other factors or variables not included in the model. This a good fit. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.829 were recorded, which indicates there is evidence of minimal autocorrelation of the residuals in the model. The F-statistic of 10.647 with p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05, indicates that the test is statistically significant of the overall model at 5% level. From the above result, procedural audit (PCA) showed a negative and insignificant effect with faithful representation (FR). That is, a one-unit increase in investigative audit services will reduce faithful representation (FR). by 0.033. However, financial audit has a negative and significant effect on faithful representation (FR). In other words, increase in financial audit (FA) on public sector in Rivers State will not improve on faithful representation (FR).

Test of Hypothesis

HO1: There is no significant effect of procedural audit on faithful representation in public sector organizations in Rivers State.

Model Summary

	Coefficients	t-statistic	p-value	Sig. level
PCA Vs FR	-0.033	-0.388	0.599	0.05
$R^2 = 0.805$ $R^2_{Adj.} = 0.784$ DW-Statistic = 1.829				

Sources: Researcher's compilation from SPSS V27

Decision: Since the significant value (P-value) of 0.599 is greater than 0.05, we therefore accept the null hypothesis one (H_{01}) and conclude that there is no significant effect of procedural audit on faithful representation in Rivers State ministries and parastatals.

Hypothesis Two:

HO2: There is no significant effect of financial audit on faithful representation in public sector organizations in Rivers State.

Model Summary

	Coefficients	t-statistic	p-value	Sig. level
FA Vs FR	-0.239	-3.860	0.000	0.05
$R^2 = 0.805$ $R^2_{Adj.} = 0.784$ DW-Statistic = 1.829				

Sources: Researcher’s compilation from SPSS V27

Decision: Since the P-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05, we therefore reject the null hypothesis three (H_{02}) and therefore conclude that there is a significant effect of financial audit on faithful representation in Rivers State ministries and parastatals.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Procedural Audit on Faithful Representation

The analysis revealed a positive but insignificant effect of procedural audit on faithful representation. This finding suggests that while there may be a tendency for procedural audit to be associated with a reduction in faithful representation, the effect is not statistically significant enough to draw strong conclusions. This study is in agreement with Akinlo and Egbetunde (2020) indicates that faithful representation is often deeply rooted in organizational culture, management practices, and systemic issues within the public sector. Therefore, while investigative audits can play a role in detecting fraud, they may not be sufficient on their own to mitigate ghost worker effectively. Additionally, the positive but insignificant correlation may be influenced by the limited scope of the audit services provided or the potential for resistance from management in public entities, which could undermine the audit's effectiveness (Owolabi & Adetula, 2022). As a result, while investigative audits serve as a necessary measure for fraud detection, their isolated impact on ghost worker remains inconclusive.

Financial Audit on Faithful Representation

The study further identified a negative and significant effect of financial audit on faithful representation. This finding is in agreement with Changwony and Rotich (2022) examined the role of internal audit function in promoting effective corporate governance of commercial banks in Kenya. The purpose of the study was to determine the role of the internal audit function in promoting effective corporate governance of commercial banks in Kenya. Survey design was adopted for the study and stratified sampling technique used in selecting the sample elements. The findings of the study revealed that internal audit has a positive and significant influence on effective corporate governance. The study concluded that internal audit function plays a positive and significant role in promoting effective corporate governance of commercial banks in Kenya. The study recommended that the audit committee should take responsibility for approving the appointment, remuneration and disengagement of the chief audit executive to enhance the effectiveness of the internal audit function.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of internal audit functions on financial reporting quality of public sector in Rivers State. Results from the study indicate that: there is no significant effect of procedural audit on faithful representation in public sector organizations in Rivers State; there is a significant effect of financial audit on faithful representation in public sector organizations in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the findings of this study therefore, the following recommendations are made

1. The management of MDAs in Rivers State should create independent audit units to carry out their audit functions independently to have effective internal control system that will lead to sound audit report.
2. The quality of audit should be maintained and improved upon by keeping audit objectives such as financial control mechanisms, implementation of Acts, rules and regulations.

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